

STUDY OF IMMOBILIZATION PROCESS OF RHIZOBACTERIA ON SOLID CARRIERS WHICH ARE THE BASIS OF THE BIOLOGICAL PRODUCT "ZAMIN-M"

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ABSTRACT

This article provides the technology of obtaining dry biological product "Zamin-M" immobilized by flocculant. The functional activity of strains has been proved during the long-term storage. The immobilized biological product "Zamin-M" was introduced as a new stimulant for cotton growing in saline conditions. This article presents the recommendations on agrotechnical methods and production of local biopreparations in agriculture.

The accumulated knowledge about the mechanisms of interaction between microorganisms and plants requires the use of minimum resource and energy costs in the purposeful design of phytomicrobial systems and optimization of their vitality to increase soil fertility, plant productivity, high plant yields, diseases and adverse conditions and stress factors. Improvement of the production technology of Zamin-M increasing the fertility of saline soils is based on scientific results. The laboratory, semi-industrial production regulation of flocculant-immobilized dry form of Zamin-M complex action has been developed based on *Pseudomonas stutzeri* SCB 308, *Bacillus megaterium* SCB 310, *Bacillus subtilis* SCB 309 strains. It is shown that the immobilized Zamin-M biological preparation having effective impact on soil

fermentative activity development and the number of useful microorganisms increases the soil fertility. The immobilized biological product "Zamin-M" was introduced as a new stimulant in cotton cultivation practice in saline conditions. There are recommendations on agrotechnics and production of local biopreparations in agriculture [1,3].

Methods and Materials:

Culture, morphological features, cell size and shape, development, shape and consistency of the colony were determined with a microscope (NSZ-405(c HDCE-X5N)). Technical specifications for the production of Zamin-M were developed and approved basing on laboratory experiments. Technical specifications were developed for the preparation form developed for the application in saline soils not lower than

Zamin-M (cell titre - 1×10^8 CFU). Developed specifications, safety regulations, acceptance conditions, test methods, transportation, storage conditions and instructions of usage include manufacturer's guarantees.

The application of Zamin-M in the form of dry powder according to the relevant Table 1

Requirements and standards for the main characteristics of Zamin-M immobilized on flocculant Gipan.

Name of indicators	Standard
1. Appearance	Fluid, yellow, granular powder
2. Colour	Specific, specific for micro biologicals
3. Total amount of moisture (%)	15%
4. Number of living cells	1×10^3
5. Number of foreign microorganisms	80%
6. Biological activity	

The working solution is sprayed at 10 ml/kg of seed by seed spraying method. Conducted in a cool place (where the sun does not fall vertically), where the air temperature is from 18°C to 30°C.

The shelf life of the product is 2 years from the time of production at 5°C+25°C. An experimental sample is developed according to the manufactured specifications and tested in vegetative and microgrowth experiments.

Findings.

The effectiveness of the biological product used to accelerate the growth and development of crops and protect them from diseases caused by phytopathogens depends largely on their commodity form. Preservation of bacterial cells in lyophilically dried form is one of the main methods of bacterial cryopreservation. There were used 3 strains of rhizobacteria from the collection of microorganisms from the Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan:

specifications depends on the navigation of plants and native microflora growing in certain soil and climatic conditions. A working solution is prepared for the application of the product. It consists of a suspension of 10×10^6 CFU [4,10].

Pseudomonas stutzeri CKB-308, *Bacillus subtilis* CKB-309, *Bacillus megaterium* CKB-310. Lyophilus is stored dried and in the form of mineral oil. These methods are not suitable for medical use and laboratory storage of cultures, they are not suitable because of the high price of the product which leads to higher production costs. The work of concentrating biomass in technological processes for the production of bacterial preparations ends with immobilization of microorganisms on appropriate carrier substrates. There are various methods of cell immobilization, especially of microorganism cells. One of them is immobilization on the solid insoluble carrier. Immobilization of bacterial cells in various solid adsorbents allows biopreparations to take a marketable form that retains stability without loss of long-term activity. For adsorption immobilization, it has the property of firmly attaching to solid carrier and gel carrier

typical for many microorganisms and likewise utilizes the natural property of maintaining viability or becoming immobile. Adsorptive immobilization involves the fact that many microorganisms attach themselves to various solid and gel-like substrates and continue their activity without movement. Adsorption methods are relatively simple and specific to "natural" methods. Essentially, immobilization occurs between a suspension of a microorganism in water and an adsorbent. Adsorbents for immobilization can be organic, inorganic, natural or artificial. The most common adsorbents can be: clay, bentonite, kulin, kurite, sand, zeolite, peat, natural silica, silicates, coal, graphite, silica gel, graphite materials, ceramics. General requirements common to all adsorbents:

- must be harmless to the cells of the host microorganism;
- be able to reliably support host microorganism cells;

- the immobilization phase between the cell and the host requires less time and effort;
- ability to remove nutrients, gaseous substrates (e.g., for aerobic cells) and waste products when working with living cells, i.e., the adsorbent material does not form diffusion barriers during metabolism and mass;
- the adsorbent must be resistant to sterilization conditions;
- in high-volume production, the most important aspect of the problem is the low cost of cell adsorption and the demand for components. [2,5,6].

The use of clay materials is associated with enhanced growth of microorganisms in the preparation of biologicals, the formation of humus in the soil and a positive effect on the aggregate state, in addition, clay mineral adsorbents protect the cells of immobilized microorganisms from extreme temperatures [6,7].

Picture 1. Transfer of Zamin-M to the kaolin carrier of different proportions.

The Ukrainian Institute of Biology studied the effect of adsorbing materials on the functional activity and viability of *Azotobacter pseudomananda*, and kaolin was

chosen as an adsorbent that meets all the above requirements. Therefore, in this work, kaolin was used as a cellular adsorbent in obtaining a dry form of the biopreparation [8].

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